

The transformation of dihydroxyphenylalanine (DOPA) to metal uptake systems and ionophores

Subramania Ranganathan* and Natarajan Tamilarasu

Discovery Laboratory, Organic III, Indian Institute of Chemical Technology, Hyderabad-500 007, India

Manuscript received 14 October 1999

The crafting of DOPA to metal uptake systems and ionophores, by attachment of ligands to the hydroxyl groups, is illustrated.

In spite of the fact that L-DOPA has found extensive therapeutic applications during the past several years, particularly with respect to the management of Parkinsonism, it has long been recognized that it is not the most ideal drug due to many reasons. The magnitude of the problem can be gauged from the fact that this orally administered substance has to reach the brain which involves several hurdles, overcoming of which results in great loss and, in addition, produces harmful metabolites. The degradation of DOPA begins even in the gastrointestinal tract and this process continues during its passage to the liver and into the blood stream. Even in the blood stream, it is continuously metabolized since the compound is unprotected either by complexation or binding to proteins. Thus the retardation of the metabolic degradation of DOPA and its efficient transport to the target sites have been the focus of the DOPA research for several years. These have resulted in improvements, although they have not solved many of the problems relating to the dissolution-adsorption-metabolism processes involving DOPA. Central to this issue is the paucity pertaining to the chemistry of DOPA. The major thrust of the present work is aimed at crafting of metal uptake systems and ionophores from DOPA. Such systems could provide DOPA with desirable properties against degradative processes described above. Further, the incorporation of such systems into a protein framework can lead to modified proteins with ion and metal uptake potential. We have recently demonstrated these very useful strategies with the transformation of tyrosine to metal uptake systems¹ and lysine to ionophores².

General strategies pursued here to transform DOPA to metal uptake systems and ionophores are presented in Chart 1.

The most promising was the simple acetylation of DOPA (1) leading to 2, since, we have recently demonstrated that the related 3-acetyltyrosine can be transformed to excellent metal uptake systems¹. In the event, all attempts to prepare 2 failed. Thus, the reaction of DOPA with AcCl/AlCl₃, which

was so effective with tyrosine, did not succeed. In an alternate approach, DOPA was transformed to the methyl ester 6, acetylated to give the triacetate 7. It was envisaged that 7 could be preferentially hydrolyzed to 8 and then by photo-

Chart 1

Fries rearrangement to the desired system 2. All attempts at preferential hydrolysis failed and only mixtures of 7 and the completely hydrolyzed 9 could be isolated (Chart 2).

Further studies were carried out with the fully protected *N*-formyl-DOPA-methyl ester 10, prepared by *N*-formylation of 6 with HCOOH/Ac₂O/NaOAc.

The clean ortho nitrosylation of phenol with (Cu(NO₃)₂)/H₂O₂ offered a strategy for 3, which being largely in the tautomeric 3a (Chart 1), can readily afford metal uptake systems. The procedure when applied to 10, gave colored

*Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri, with affection, admiration and regards on the occasion of his 75th birthday.

Chart 2

intractable products. Interestingly, treatment of **10** with $\text{NaNO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ gave a crystalline mono-nitro compound. Unfortunately, the NMR spectrum clearly showed that it arose from the only undesirable option, namely, substitution at the 6-position, since at the remaining available positions, 2 and 5 would have opportunity for elaboration to metal uptake systems of the type 3. The nitro compound has been assigned structure **11**. Acetylation to **12** confirmed structural assignments (Chart 3).

In view of the problems encountered in ring substitution, the strategy was changed to the further elaboration of the existing ligands. This approach has produced positive results.

Alkylation of **10** with dimethyl bromomalonate in NaH/DMF afforded a mono-*O*-alkylated product. The expectation was that the dianion precursor would undergo alkylation at the relatively less acidic 4-position. In the event, the monoalkylated compound obtained in 24% yield turned out to be the 3-*O*-alkylated product **13**. The structural assignment is based on the NMR spectrum, which showed significant downfield shift of the 6-H compared to the parent one. Interestingly, compound **13** readily formed a copper complex with methanolic copper acetate, to which structure **13a** has been assigned (Chart 3). Attempted purification of **13a** led to extensive decomposition. Alkylation with 2-bromo-pentane-1,3-dione should give products where the metal complexes should be well stable. Further, compound **13** would be an excellent starting point to several DOPA derivatives, an important one being the attachment of uracil moiety with urea.

Of particular interest would be metal π -complexes of DOPA. In the present work, the preparation of such complexes from Pt and Pd were explored by attachment of proxi-

mate terminal π -containing ligands.

The reaction of **10** with excess allyl bromide in $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{DMF}$ afforded three pure compounds, namely, *N*-formyl-DOPA-(3-*O*-allyl)-OMe (**14**; 20%), *N*-formyl-DOPA-(4-*O*-allyl)-OMe (**15**; 30%) and *N*-formyl-DOPA-(3,4-bis-*O*-allyl)-OMe (**16**; 9%) (Chart 4). The structural assignments are based on NMR and mass spectral data. Several attempts to prepare Pt and Pd complexes with **16** failed. This is most likely to be difficulties in aligning the proximate double bonds in the required orientation. Compound **16** is a noteworthy derivative of DOPA. The double bonds make further elaboration possible, a useful one would be the hydroboration oxidation to diols that can be converted into ionophores (*vide infra*).

Promising results were obtained from endeavors to attach ionophore arms to DOPA. Thus **10** with excess methoxyethoxymethyl [MEM]chloride in aqueous sodium carbonate afforded only the mono-protected derivative, which on the basis of NMR has been assigned the 4-alkylated structure **17**. The mass spectrum of **17** is noteworthy. It showed, in addition to the MH^+ at 328, a strong band at 350 corresponding to the uptake of sodium ion. This was confirmed by doping with sodium perchlorate, when the parent peak disappeared, the base peak being at 350 corresponding to near total complexation with sodium ion **17** leading to **18** (Chart 5). Similar results were obtained by doping with lithium perchlorate.

Preliminary transport experiments² have shown promising results. Work is in progress to prepare a series of compounds related to **17**, and study their transport comprehensively, *in vivo* and *in vitro*.

In conclusion, exploration of the sparse chemistry of DOPA has afforded promising leads in the design of metal uptake systems and ionophores.

Chart 3

Chart 4

Chart 5

Experimental

Proton NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker WM 400 (400 MHz), Bruker WP 80 (80 MHz) and Hitachi R 600 (60 MHz) instruments. The chemical shifts were recorded in ppm with TMS at 0 as the internal standard. IR spectra were recorded on PE 580/1600 instruments, either as neat liquids or as KBr pellets. FAB mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX 120/DA-6000 spectrometer data system using

argon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature with *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix. Elemental analyses were carried out in an automatic C, H, N analyser. Silica gel was used for tlc. Reactions were monitored wherever possible by tlc. The organic extracts were invariably dried over anhyd. $MgSO_4/NaSO_4$ and solvents evaporated *in vacuo*.

3,4-Dihydroxyphenylalanine methyl ester hydrochloride [DOPA-OMe.HCl] (6): To a stirred and ice-cooled dry MeOH (25 ml), was added, in drops, SOCl₂ (2.5 ml, 36.25 mmol) followed by L-DOPA (5 g, 25 mmol). The reaction mixture was allowed to attain room temperature and refluxed for 10 h, then solvents evaporated under vacuo and the residue on crystallization from dry EtOH-Et₂O gave **6** (5.3 g, 85%), m.p. 174° (lit. 170–171°); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3406 br, 1742, 1611, 1528, 1446 cm⁻¹; δ (D₂O) 3.06 (2H, d, C ^{β} H₂), 3.72 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.25 (1H, t, C ^{α} H), 6.69 (3H, m, ArH).

N,O,O'-Triacetyl-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine methyl ester (7): To a stirred suspension of DOPA-OMe.HCl (**6**; 1.2 g, 4.8 mmol) in acetic anhydride (6 ml) was added pyridine (1 ml, 12.3 mmol). After stirring for 5 h at 25°, water (20 ml) was added and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (4×20 ml). The CH₂Cl₂ extract was washed with 2 N HCl (3×8 ml), saturated NaHCO₃ solution, water (2×8 ml), dried and evaporated to give as white solid (1.63 g, 82%), m.p. 116°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3322, 2956, 1735, 1642, 1530, 1504, cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.0 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 2.28 (6H, s, 2×OCOCH₃), 3.16 (2H, d, C ^{β} H₂), 3.75 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.91 (1H, q, C ^{α} H), 6.19 (1H, d, NH), 6.91–7.22 (3H, m, ArH).

N-Acetyl-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine methyl ester (9): A solution of **7** (0.66 g, 2 mmol) in MeOH (10 ml) was treated with aqueous NaHCO₃ (0.168 g, 2 mmol; 6 ml) and stirred at room temperature for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated to about 6 ml and acidified with 10% HCl, extracted with EtOAc (3×15 ml), dried and evaporated to give **9** as a thick syrup (0.38 g, 75%) (Found: C, 57.87; H, 5.97; N, 5.97. C₁₂H₁₅NO₅ calcd. for: C, 56.91; H, 5.91; N, 5.53%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3320 br, 1730, 1713, 1695, 1666, 1650, 1537 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.9 (3H, s, NCOCH₃), 2.92 (2H, d, C ^{β} H₂), 3.65 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.7 (1H, q, C ^{α} H), 5.92 (1H, d, NH), 6.28–6.85 (3H, m, ArH).

N-Formyl-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine methyl ester [N-formyl-DOPA-OMe] (10): To a stirred and ice-cooled mixture of L-DOPA-OMe.HCl (1.24 g, 5 mmol) and sodium formate (0.374 g, 5.5 mmol) in formic acid (12.5 ml), was added acetic anhydride (5 ml). After stirring for 3 h at room temperature, MeOH (8 ml) was added with ice-cooling and stirring continued for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then evaporated, the residue dissolved in EtOAc (45 ml) and filtered. The filtrate was washed with 10% HCl (8 ml), saturated NaHCO₃ solution and saturated NaCl solution (8 ml), dried and evaporated. The residue on crystallization from EtOAc-hexane gave **10** as a white solid (1.14 g, 95%), m.p. 123° (lit. 119–121°) (Found: C, 54.36; H, 5.08; N, 5.64

C₁₁H₁₃NO₅ calcd. for: C, 55.23; H, 5.44; N, 5.85%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3526, 3348, 1728, 1632, 1533, 1433 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃-DMSO-d₆) 3.0 (2H, d, C ^{β} H₂), 3.72 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.81 (1H, q, C ^{α} H), 6.38–6.88 (3H, m, ArH), 7.06 (1H, d, NH), 8.16 (1H, s, CHO); m/z 240 (MH)⁺.

N-Formyl-3,4-dihydroxy-6-nitrophenylalanine methyl ester (11): To a stirred and ice-cooled mixture of **10** (0.239 g, 1 mmol) and sodium nitrite (0.152 g, 2.2 mmol) in water (5 ml); was added, in drops, 2.5 M H₂SO₄ (0.67 ml, 1.75 mmol). After stirring at room temperature for 2 h, the reaction mixture was extracted with EtOAc (5×15 ml), washed with water (2×5 ml), dried and evaporated. The residue on crystallization from EtOAc-hexane gave **11** as yellow solid (0.235 g, 83%), m.p. 168–169°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3403, 3322, 1720, 1651, 1597, 1537, 1334, 1308 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃-DMSO-d₆) 2.94–3.50 (2H, m, C ^{β} H₂), 3.72 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.88 (1H, m, C ^{α} H), 6.81 (1H, s, ArH) 7.28–7.75 (2H, m, NH+ArH), 8.13 (1H, s, CHO); m/z 285 (MH)⁺.

N-Formyl(O,O'-diacetyl)-3,4-dihydroxy-6-nitrophenylalanine methyl ester (12): To stirred suspension of **11** (0.1 g, 0.35 mmol) in acetic anhydride (1 ml), was added pyridine (0.1 ml, 1.23 mmol). After stirring the mixture for 3 h at room temperature, water (8 ml) was added and extracted with EtOAc (5×15 ml). The EtOAc extract was washed with 2 N HCl (2×8 ml), saturated NaHCO₃ solution (4×8 ml) and water (2×5 ml) dried and evaporated *in vacuo* to give **12** as reddish yellow gum (0.106 g, 82%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3368, 1734, 1654, 1597, 1534, 1331 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.35 (6H, s, 2×OCOCH₃) 3.54 (2H, m, C ^{β} H₂), 3.78 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.0 (1H, q, C ^{α} H), 6.63 (1H, d, NH), 7.25 (1H, s, ArH), 7.89 (1H, s, ArH), 8.26 (1H, s, CHO).

N-Formyl(3-O-dimethyl malonate)-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine methyl ester (13): To a stirred and ice-cooled solution of *N*-formyl-DOPA-OMe (**10**; 0.12 g, 0.5 mmol) in DMF (3 ml), was added NaH (50%; 0.024 g, 1 mmol). After stirring the reddish brown solution for 0.5 h, methyl bromomalonate (0.211 g, 1 mmol) in DMF (1 ml) was added to it and stirring continued at room temperature for 8 h. After acidifying the reaction mixture with 2 N HCl, water (5 ml) was added, extracted with EtOAc (4×10 ml), dried and evaporated *in vacuo*. The crude product on purification through a silica gel column (EtOAc : PhH :: 1 : 9) gave **13** as a thick syrup (0.045 g, 24%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3418 br, 2923, 2852, 1733, 1684, 1652, 1558, 1506 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 3.05 (2H, d, C ^{β} H₂), 3.74 (3H, s, dopa ester), 3.85 (6H, s, malonic 2×COOCH₃), 4.32 (1H, m, malonic CH), 4.89 (1H, q, C ^{α} H), 6.1 (1H, d, NH), 6.58–6.9 (3H, m, ArH), 7.1 (1H, s, phenolic OH), 8.09 (1H, s, CHO); m/z 369 (M)⁺.

Reaction of 10 with allyl bromide. Preparation of N-formyl(O,O'-bis-allyl)-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine methyl ester (16), N-formyl(4-O'-allyl)-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine methyl ester (15) and N-formyl(3-O'-allyl)-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine methyl ester (14) : To a stirred mixture of **10** (0.239 g, 1 mmol) and K_2CO_3 (0.276 g, 2 mmol) in DMF (5 ml), was added allyl bromide (0.242 g, 2 mmol) at room temperature. After stirring for 6 h, the reaction mixture was filtered, the filtrate admixed with water (10 ml), extracted with EtOAc (3×10 ml), washed with 2 N HCl, dried and evaporated. TLC of the residue showed three products (EtOAc, R_f 0.65, 0.55, 0.51). Chromatographic separation on silica gel column (EtOAc : PhH :: 1 : 4) gave **16** (0.027 g, 8.5%; R_f 0.65, EtOAc), **15** (0.084 g, 30%; R_f 0.51, EtOAc) and **14** (0.056 g, 20%; R_f 0.55, EtOAc) as thick gummy compounds : **16** ν_{max} (neat) 3314 br, 2924, 2856, 1744, 1683, 1513 1425 cm^{-1} ; (CDCl₃) δ 2.95 (2H, d $C^\beta H_2$), 3.75 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.43 (4H, d, 2×OCH₂), 4.79 (1H, q, $C^\alpha H$), 5.0–5.5 (4H, m, 2×=CH₂), 5.66–6.23 (3H, m, NH + 2×=CH), 6.36–6.80 (3H, m, ArH), 7.96 (1H, s, CHO); m/z 319 (M)⁺; **15** ν_{max} (neat) 3340 br, 2925, 1742, 1672, 1599, 1514, 1437 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl₃) 3.09 (2H, d, $C^\beta H_2$), 3.78 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.59 (2H, d, OCH₂), 4.97 (1H, q, $C^\alpha H$), 5.19–5.63 (2H, m, =CH₂), 5.81–6.44 (3H, m, NH + =CH- + aromatic C-6 H), 6.53–6.97 (2H, m aromatic C-2 H + aromatic C-5 H), 8.22 (1H, s, CHO); m/z 280 (MH)⁺; **14** ν_{max} (neat) 3342 br, 3028, 2928, 2953, 1742, 1672, 1595, 1513 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl₃) 3.06 (2H, d,

$C^\beta H_2$), 3.69 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.56 (2H, d, OCH₂), 4.94 (1H, q, $C^\alpha H$), 5.19–5.59 (2H, m, =CH₂), 5.84–6.31 (2H, m, NH + =CH-), 6.41–7.0 (3H, m, ArH), 8.25 (1H, s, CHO); m/z 280 (MH)⁺

N-Formyl(3-O'-methoxyethoxymethyl)-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine methyl ester (17) : To a stirred solution of *N*-formyl-DOPA-OMe (**10**; 0.478 g, 2 mmol) in 10% aqueous Na₂CO₃ (10 ml) was added methoxyethoxymethyl chloride (0.992 g, 8 mmol). After stirring for 3 h at room temperature, the reaction mixture was extracted with EtOAc (5×15 ml), washed with water (2×5 ml), dried and evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue on purification through a silica gel column (EtOAc : PhH :: 1 : 4) gave **17** as a thick syrup (48%); ν_{max} (neat) 3340 br, 2950, 1731, 1652, 1594, 1510, 1439 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl₃) 3.03 (2H, d, $C^\beta H_2$), 3.44 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.53–3.81 (7H, m, CH₂CH₂ + COOCH₃), 4.69–4.97 (3H, m, OCH₂O + $C^\alpha H$), 6.5 (1H, d, ArH), 6.7 (1H, s, ArH), 6.81 (1H, d, ArH), 7.03 (1H, d, NH), 8.19 (1H, s, CHO); m/z 328 (MH)⁺.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful for financial support from D.S.T., New Delhi.

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